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A Survey on the Use of Projective Techniques

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to explore the Filipino counselors' explanations to and in favor of the use of projective techniques in their work. A researcher-constructed survey questionnaire was used in gathering the data. A total of 49 professionals consisting of Registered Guidance Counselors (37%), Registered Psychometricians (35%), and Registered Psychologists (12%) were included in the study. The survey revealed that 65% of the respondents reported to be using projectives in their counseling work such as human figure drawing tests and sentence completion tests. However, it was also revealed that most of the participants lack intensive training on projective techniques (33%). The practice of caution in using projective techniques and provisions on critical examination and proper use of assessment must be emphasized early during training and must be enhanced during graduate courses. This is to ensure that counselors-in-training are updated on the current researchers and are more likely to use evidence-based approaches in their practice.

Keywords: *projective techniques, psychological assessment*

Introduction

The use of projective techniques can be traced back in history which implies the extent of how these techniques are used in assessment, commonly among children and adolescents (Cashel, 2002; Dyer, 2018), relied upon by school psychologists (Hughes et al., 2010), and applied in forensic settings (Erickson et al., 2007).

In counseling, psychological tests are being employed for diagnostic, evaluative and therapeutic decisions (Datu, 2012). However, interpreting test results according to the original tests were proven to be risky, if not dangerous, due to lack of cross cultural comparisons (Datu, 2012), cultural limitations (Lilienfeld et al., 2000) and bias towards non-equivalent translations (Bernaldo, 2011) since most of these tests were constructed in the Western context.

The stronger risk is geared towards the use of projective techniques as criticisms on its limited validity and reliability have increased in the past years (Lilienfeld et al., 2000). Such controversy with regards to the reliability and validity has also leaked out on testimonies by mental health experts in family court, which, according to literature, is partially based on the perception that many mental health professionals formulate their expert opinions based upon pseudoscientific assessment techniques that contribute to erroneous clinical conclusions (Emery, 2005; Otto et al., 2000; Erickson et al., 2007).

The attitudes toward projective techniques have been blatantly negative in professional training setting yet guardedly positive in clinical practice (Hardwood et al., 2011). Projective techniques were claimed to be unfairly singled out by criticism that can only be described as abhorrent from a particular subset of critics. Even though projective techniques are consistently criticized, mental health practitioners from different countries to continue to rely on the Rorschach, Thematic measures, Human-Figure-Drawings, and Sentence Completion tests as part of the clinical assessment (Piotrowski, 2015).

In 2016, a survey on the use of projective techniques among Filipino Counselors was conducted. Lopez et al. (2016) documented the practices in the use of these techniques among Filipino Counselors. It was found that majority of the Filipino Counselors who participated in the study (41%) reported to be using projective techniques in their work, with higher preferences for sentence completion and human figure drawings. The use of these tests were claimed to be for assessment purposes despite of the lack of rigorous, supervised preparation for the proper utilization of such tests.

It is important to note that the findings of Lopez et al. (2016) suggest that counselors who employ projective techniques may be less concerned about getting adequately trained in the use of, and gaining knowledge of new information about projective techniques. If the current literature about projective techniques reflect questions regarding their reliability, validity, incremental validity and treatment utility (Lilienfeld et al., 2000), does this, in any way, explains why they tend to view further training regarding projective techniques of a lesser priority? What could be the reasons for the Filipino counselors to continuously use projective techniques despite the numerous criticism and controversies in the research literature?

In exploring this, the researcher wish to draw from the theory of reasoned action which proposes that behavior is influenced by the attitudes toward such behavior and the subjective norm, or the beliefs about what others think they should do (DeBono, 2019). Intention or instrumentality, or the belief that the behavior will lead to the intended outcome, is the best predictor of behavior. Instrumentality is determined by three things: their attitude toward the specific behavior, their subjective norms, and their perceived behavioral control. It is said that, the more favorable the attitude and the subjective norms and the greater the perceived control, the stronger the person's intention to perform the behavior (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975).

Tentatively guided by the Theory of Reasoned Action (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980; Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975), the researcher intended to

understand the experiences leading to the continuous use of projective techniques in the counseling setting despite its criticisms, controversies, and lack of sufficient scientific evidences. Previous researches (Lilienfeld et al., 2000) identified critical examination of the use of projective tools but the lack of interest on getting adequately trained and gaining new information about them (Lopez et al., 2016). In this vein, it was deemed helpful to use the theory as tentative framework as identifying the factors affecting the mentioned behaviors will also aid in identifying the most effective and appropriate intervention and training program in the counseling education. The framework will tentatively serve as guide in exploring the Filipino counselors' explanations to and in favor of the use of projective techniques, what motivates them to continuously use it, and finally to identify the reasons that explain the continuous use of such techniques.

Methodology

Participants

A total of 49 professionals consisting of Registered Guidance Counselors (37%), Registered Psychometrician (35%), Registered Psychologists (12%), both Registered Guidance Counselor and Psychometrician (10%), and people working in related fields such as Childlife Specialist and Guidance Associate (6%). In terms of education, 18.37% of the participants obtained Bachelor's degrees, 69% held Master's degrees (holder/with units), and 12% held Doctoral degrees or were enrolled in doctoral programs at the time of data collection. The participants' ages ranged from 21-56 years old ($M=34.14$ years; $SD=8.48$).

Instruments

A researcher-constructed survey questionnaire was used in gathering the data. The questionnaire included questions for demographic information, open-ended questions, and statements to which the participant rated their perceptions.

Data Analysis

The first part of this study utilized descriptive statistics where data were to be interpreted using frequencies and percentages. Responses were encoded, categorized and interpreted using frequencies and percentages. The second part consisting of open-ended questions was analyzed using content analysis.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure ethical research, this study followed and respected the principles of research ethics which respect a person's autonomy, beneficence and non-maleficence, justice, informed consent, confidentiality and data protection, integrity, and conflict of interest.

Results and Discussion

With the aim of exploring the continuous use of projective techniques, the participants were asked about their use of projective techniques. The study found that, overall, 65% or 32 participants reported using projective techniques in their work, while the other 35% or 17 participants were non-users. The participants were asked to evaluate the importance of using projective techniques in their work as well as the extent of their awareness on the current researches on the projective techniques which was shown in Table 1.

It was found that though the respondents reported to be using projective techniques in their practice, the overall use could be described as moderate. The extent of their awareness on the current researches on projective techniques could be accounted for their use of such techniques in their practice. It appeared that these professionals are using other techniques and are aware of the current researches but still opt to use projective techniques in their practice.

Table 1. *Participant's Evaluation on the Projective Techniques*

<i>Evaluation on the Projective Techniques</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Extent of use of Projective Techniques in Practice	4.42	2.99
Extent of awareness on the current researches on Projective Techniques	4.51	2.38

Users of projective techniques enumerated the techniques they use in practice. Table 2 shows that they prefer using the human figure drawing tests and sentence completion tests. This could be attributed to the fact that such tests are easy to administer and requires lesser materials than TAT, Bender and Rorschach.

Table 2. *Projective Techniques used in Practice*

<i>Projective Techniques</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Draw-A-Person-Test	25	1
House-Tree-Person	16	2
Sentence Completion Test	15	3
Kinetic Family Drawing	14	4
Thematic Apperception Test	12	5
Bender-Gestalt Test	2	6
Rorschach Inkblot Test	1	7

Table 3. *Reported Purpose in using Projective Techniques*

<i>Purpose</i>
Deeper understanding of the client
Validate results of objective test
Assessment
Trauma
Determine intellectual capacity
Determine personality
Relationships
Further evaluate the unconscious/underlying issues
Get more information to clients with limited verbal response
Build rapport with the client
For instruction purposes

The use of projective techniques among professionals serve various purposes. The responses gathered from the open-ended questions were categorized in the current study and presented in Table 3. It was found that projective techniques were utilized to gain deeper understanding of the clients. It was reported that these techniques allow those clients who have limited verbal ability or simply do not want to talk to express themselves. Others indicated that projective techniques are tools for them to build rapport with the clients, most especially children. There are also respondents who reported that projective techniques were used to supplement and validate results from objective tests, and to assess and evaluate the client in some areas such as trauma, intellectual capacity, personality, and relationships. There are respondents who indicated that they only utilize projective techniques for instructional purposes.

Table 4. *Reported Essential Information derived from Projective Techniques*

<i>Essential Information</i>
Deeper understanding of the client
Unconscious motives and behavioral tendencies
Inner conflicts, issues and thought processes
Self-concept
Coping and defense mechanisms
Trauma history
Relationships
Emotions and anxiety

With regards to the information derived from projective techniques, there are respondents who still reported deeper understanding of the client as essential information. Such deeper understanding may be supported by what other respondents' reported essential information from projective techniques as summarized in Table 4. These includes those that were indicated in the manuals for administering projective techniques which include the unconscious motives and behavioral tendencies, inner conflicts, issues and thought processes, client's self-concept and coping and defense mechanisms, trauma history, relationships as well as issues therein, and client's emotions and anxiety.

Table 5. *Trainings on Projective Techniques Attended*

<i>Trainings Attended</i>	<i>Frequency (n=49)</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
None	16	33
Graduate School	11	22
Bachelor's Degree	9	18
Trainings and Seminars (PGCA, PAP, CPD Trainings)	5	10
Doctorate Degree Courses	4	8
In-service Training/Practicum	4	8

In terms of preparation and trainings, results in Table 5 suggest that most of the participants lack intensive training on projective techniques as majority (33%) admitted to have not attended any training. Most of them have learned projective techniques only from graduate school and during undergraduate degree. Only a number (8%) actually received rigorous formal training through doctorate degree coursework.

The current study also explored the trainings that the respondents would like to attend is shown in Table 6. Most of the respondents expressed interest to be trained in Rorschach Inkblot Test particularly the new scoring system (37%). There is a number as well who would like attend training on the proper administration, interpretation and report writing using projective tests (31%).

Table 6. Trainings on Projective Techniques Respondents would like to Attend

Trainings	Frequency (n=49)	Percentage
Rorschach Inkblot Test (new scoring system)	18	37
Proper Administration, Interpretation and Report Writing	15	31
Thematic Apperception Test	5	10
Proper Projective Techniques to Use and its Accuracy	4	8
Drawing Test (KFD, DAP and HTP)	3	6
None	3	6
Test Development	1	2

When sought opinion with regards to teaching projective techniques among new practitioners, most of the respondents expressed agreement (67%), while the rest indicated non-agreement. Table 7 shows the reasons for agreement in teaching projective techniques. Majority of those who agreed indicated that projective techniques are useful in understanding client's underlying issues and that they are sources of essential information. Interestingly, those who agreed also indicated that such may be taught but emphasized on supervision from a trained professional.

Table 7. Reasons for Agreement to Teaching Projective Techniques among New Practitioners

Reasons	Frequency (n=33)	Percentage
Understand client's underlying issues	8	24
Useful and essential information from the test	7	21
With supervision from a trained professional	5	15
Validation of objective findings (deeper assessment)	4	12
Easy to administer and respond	4	12
Ideal assessment tool	2	6
If used with other techniques	2	6
To help other people	1	3

The reasons for non-agreement, on the other hand, were shown in Table 8. It was found that those who disagreed in teaching projective techniques among new practitioners had emphasized the importance of training and experience as well as license to practice and qualifications in using projective techniques. It was also found that there are respondents who are aware of the validity issues of projective techniques and was able to utilize other kinds of assessment tool such as clinical interviewing which they seem to find more helpful.

Table 8. Reasons for Non-Agreement to Teaching Projective Techniques among New Practitioners

Reasons	Frequency (n=16)	Percentage
Training and Experience	7	44
License to Practice and Qualifications	4	25
There are other kinds of assessment tool such as clinical interviewing	3	19
Validity issues	2	13

Conclusions

The present study is a continuation of the study conducted by Lopez et al. (2016) and attempted to explore the practitioner's continuous practice in using projective techniques. Most of the respondents reported to be utilizing projective techniques in their practice despite knowledge on current researchers, but seems to incorporate such technique with other assessment tools. Only a few of them received formal training as there are respondents who reported to have learned the technique through seminars and undergraduate coursework. Compared with the study of Lopez et al. (2016), the respondents seem more aware on the recent researchers as evident in the extent of how they use it, emphasis on supervision, proper administration, training and experience, validity issues, and exploration of other assessment tools such as clinical interviewing.

The study also revealed that the respondents seem to be more cautious in using projective techniques in their practice despite continuous use as they seem to depend on such in determining essential information about the client. It is interesting to note that though the respondents are aware of the current researches, they still use it in their practice. This continuous use may be attributed to how one was trained in the undergraduate level where most received training on projective techniques and how the practice seems to become apparent among the future practitioners. It could be noted that the respondents find projective techniques as a favorable tool and that it is a practice that they find to be customary among psychology majors due to the essential information from projective techniques they have indicated and was revealed in this study. It is said that, the more favorable the attitude and the subjective norms and the greater the perceived control, the person's intention to perform the behavior is stronger. Hence, it appears that as long as they believe that such essential information can be found only from projective techniques, the projective techniques will always find its way in practice.

The practice of caution in using projective techniques must start in the early level of training, particularly in undergraduate degree. Provisions on critical examination and proper use of assessment must be emphasized early during training and must be enhanced during graduate courses. This is to ensure that practitioners-in-training are updated on the current researchers and are more likely to use evidence-based approaches in their practice.

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